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**Challenging Notions of African Masculinities through
Post-Apartheid Queer Cinemas**

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ABSTRACT

In this dissertation I examine the representations of masculinity and sexuality in post-apartheid queer films, focusing primarily on the South African films *Inxeba (The Wound)* (John Trengove, 2017), *While You Weren't Looking* (Catherine Stewart, 2015), *Skoonheid (Beauty)* (Oliver Hermanus, 2011) and *Die Stropers (The Harvesters)* (Etienne Kallos, 2018). By investigating the challenges some of these films encountered during their production, distribution and reception, I aim to examine how the so-called 'crisis of masculinity' manifested itself in post-apartheid South African society. My goal is to examine whether these films contribute to contemporary debates on masculinity and sexuality in South Africa. The continuous engagement with the subject by local filmmakers and artists, despite the many obstacles, bodes well, not only for the film industry but also for the ongoing struggle for gender equality.

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LIST OF SELECTED ABBREVIATIONS

ANC	African National Congress
Contralesa	Congress of Traditional Leaders of South Africa
FPB	Film and Publication Board (South Africa)
LGBTQ	Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, and Queer
MBF	Man and Boy Foundation (South Africa)
NFVF	National Film and Video Foundation (South Africa)
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NHTL	National House of Traditional Leaders (South Africa)
SADF	South African Defence Force

LIST OF SELECTED FOREIGN WORDS

<u>Afrikaans</u>	<u>English</u>
<i>boer</i>	farmer
<i>moffie</i>	faggot
<i>skoonheid</i>	beauty
<i>volk</i>	nation
<i>volksmoeder</i>	mother of the nation

<u>Xhosa</u>	<u>English</u>
<i>amadoda</i>	Xhosa men who have achieved manhood
<i>indoda</i>	a man who has achieved manhood through <i>ulwaluko</i>
<i>ulwaluko</i>	traditional circumcision and initiation into manhood

<u>Zulu</u>	<u>English</u>
<i>injonga</i>	active male partner in homosexual anal intercourse

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If you are neutral in situations of injustice, you have chosen the side of the oppressor.

— Desmond Tutu, quoted in Brown 1984, p.19

PREFACE

Queer as a term

Debate continues about the proper taxonomies in studies of divergent African sexual and gender orientations (Osinubi 2019a). Martin Botha explicitly cautions against misleading Western LGBTQ terminology which may be ‘understood as signifying homogeneity in a group that is massively diverse’ (2016, pp.6–7). Botha (2016) selects the term ‘queer’ as indicating a space in which various notions of gender and sexuality, and sexual identity, orientation and behaviour, can be examined, despite queer theory itself having arisen from the gay rights movement in the West, and use of the term ‘queer’ predominantly reflecting Western concerns (Epprecht 2008). Some scholars prefer reference to ‘nonnormative sexualities’, but seem to apply terms interchangeably (Epprecht 2011; Chiang and Wong 2016; Osinubi 2018).

Throughout this dissertation I use the term ‘queer’ to suggest more than nonnormative or same-sex sexualities, a political framework proposed by Hakima Abbas and Sokari Ekine (2013): ‘a perspective that embraces sexual plurality and seeks to transform, overhaul and revolutionise African order rather than to seek to assimilate into oppressive hetero-patriarchal-capitalist frameworks’ (p.3). The term ‘queer’ suggests several and diverse sexual and gender identities (Durkin 2017) and engages with current debates in African feminist and critical masculinity studies (Epprecht 2008).

INTRODUCTION

The themes explored in queer cinemas are complex, nowhere more so than in Africa where, according to Sylvia Tamale (2007), homosexuality epitomises one of the last strongholds of legally backed and state-sanctioned oppression. Queer rights are outlawed in thirty-two African countries and nonnormative sex punishable by death in as many as four (Mendos 2019). Inside Africa, queer rights create an enduring and contentious discourse. Homosexuality was decriminalised in Botswana in June 2019, but just a month earlier the Supreme Court of Kenya refused to overturn same-sex discrimination laws in force since colonial times (BBC News 2019). The authority of colonial legislation and religious doctrine weighs heavily on contemporary societies and legal and constitutional guarantees of rights, like those in South Africa, do not guarantee social acceptance, or end discrimination (Balseiro and Masilela 2003; Osinubi 2019b; Reid 2013).

Marc Epprecht (2008) traces the intellectual discourse on African sexualities from Western adventurers and ethnographers of the late 1800s through Freudian psychology to African authors such as Jomo Kenyatta, Ali Mazrui and Frantz Fanon, three African scholars critical of Western scholarship in Africa but not averse 'to accept or to actively promote' Western notions that there was no homosexuality in Africa (pp.131–132). Scholars like them were complicit in creating the myth that homosexuality was absent from precolonial African societies (Botha 2014). Epprecht (2011) identified portrayal of African men as 'reduced to metaphorical boyhood or even raped by racist whites or Arabs' as a primary theme in African fiction (p.154). Epprecht (2013b) also claims that European officials, industrialists, journalists and scholars colluded to keep secrets about same-sex sexuality in Africa. They actively promoted the idea that there was no place in Africa for 'people who did not conform to heterosexual norms' because:

the stereotype of close-to-nature Africans just didn't fit with the popular stereotype of homosexuality as a manifestation of decadence or over-

civilization. Since the idea of Africa's primitivity was so crucial to the justification of colonial rule, it had to be defended, even subconsciously, by ruling out investigations that might complicate the picture (p.42).

This topic is controversial and divisive. Scholars across African societies have to contend with denouncements from politicians and clergy that nonnormative sexualities are un-African (Livermon 2018; Osinubi 2018). There is no single African sexuality, argues Xavier Livermon (2018), as much as there is no single 'gay identity' (Botha 2014; Gevisser and Cameron 1995). Instead, sexualities are as much shaped by Africans themselves through discourse and political wrangling. Homosexuality plays a small part in the wider debate about identity and race, while Africa as an epistemological object of knowledge remains somewhat 'unresolved' (Green-Simms 2018, p.653). Diverse international, pan-African and national considerations of the various possible meanings of both 'Africa' and 'homosexuality,' and how these terms 'with their varying histories and modes of othering' may be understood, have been central to the discourse (Hoad 2007).

Despite the existence of a substantial body of scholarship on sexuality in Africa, Taiwo Adetunji Osinubi (2018) believes there is a dramatic lack of research within cultural studies. Osinubi suggests that the large and growing number of recent representations of queer sexualities in literature, film and other arts—as well as a developing public debate—make African queer scholarship an expanding area of research (2018, pp.598–599).

The reluctance of African film scholars to engage with the subject of sexuality is noteworthy. As an example, there is no mention of queer, gay or LGBTQ films in the first historical publications about African cinema from the 1990s (Diawara 1992; Ukadike 1994; Barlet 2000). These authors focused rather on the postcolonial and political contexts of African film, unsurprising therein that African filmmaking was birthed from oppression and resistance (Ukadike 2014); from what Carmela Garritano (2013) calls 'the historical and political struggle of decolonization' (p.1). In a posthumous essay, Esiaba Irobi (2014) argues that too much emphasis was placed 'on

the social, political and economic difficulties faced by African filmmakers' despite the contributions of distinguished scholars such as Mbye Cham, Diawara, Ukadike, Teshome Gabriel and Keyan Tomaselli (p.24).

The early pan-Africanist movement within film scholarship was inclined to disregard Africa's cultural diversity and national histories. This approach was problematic because representing 'Africa as a "nation" of some homogeneous identity [...] has elements of Western political and cultural perceptions embedded within it' (Mhando 2014, p.14). More recently, however, the many different cinematic experiences in Africa are acknowledged in an attempt to understand African cinema on its own terms and to identify the influences and discourses at work within it (Bakari 2000).

Irobi (2014) directs much criticism against African filmmakers who lack in-depth knowledge of indigenous African semiology, challenging them to create more sophisticated, more complex films which are not 'amateurish, and skip over the surface of African life and cultural intelligence' (p.40). Irobi laments the bulk of African cinematic practices as 'untheorized' and cautions against any attempt at a unified theory of African cinema. Irobi also suggests that a meaningful approach to African cinema theory would rather be 'to use one's own indigenous culture as metonymic or selectively representative' of what is generally thought of as 'African' because 'every African society, community, or culture' will have its own theories of the arts (2014, pp.23–42). Inasmuch, one could argue that instead of attempting a definition of a homogeneous 'queer Africa' or 'queer African cinema,' one could examine the complex experiences of individual queer societies in Africa and thereby establish a theoretical framework within which broader concepts can be (re-)defined.

South Africa started on the path of dramatic political transformation in 1991, culminating in the 1996 promulgation of a new constitution and a bill of rights which includes a now famous liberal equality clause (Appendix 1). Despite being groundbreaking in terms of constitutional rights for queer people, patriarchal and homophobic attitudes still dominate societal values in South Africa, with a pervasive lack of societal

acceptance of sexual and gender minorities (Reid 2013). Sexuality unexpectedly became one of South Africa's principal arenas of political contestation (Posel 2005).

The protection the constitution offers all citizens, regardless of sexual orientation, gender or race, has triggered a 'crisis of masculinity' in South Africa, exacerbated by the transition towards gender/power relations embodied in the constitution (Walker 2005, p.161; Reid and Walker 2005; Sideris 2005; Mchunu 2007). Such a crisis is usually triggered by instability and uncertainty over social roles, identity, relationships (occupational and social), the erosion of patriarchy, and sexuality (Frosh et al. 2002; Mchunu 2007). Graeme Reid and Liz Walker (2005) point to the fact that South Africa's transition to democracy unsettled colonial and apartheid masculinities, all widely considered to be 'patriarchal, authoritarian and steeped in violence' (p.8). Recent critical studies on men and masculinity in South Africa focused on the notion of such a 'crisis of masculinity,' studies which Robert Morrell (2005) argues should rightly be treated with suspicion. Although there is no doubt, adds Morrell, South Africa's men are behaving differently, especially 'in the realm of sexuality.' While some men responded positively, 'others have experienced crises of identity' (pp.xi–xii).

This study is based on detailed analyses of four post-apartheid queer feature films with contemporary narratives which have all been released theatrically in South Africa—*Inxeba (The Wound)* (John Trengove, 2017), *While You Weren't Looking* (Catherine Stewart, 2015), *Scoonheid (Beauty)* (Oliver Hermanus, 2011) and *Die Stropers (The Harvesters)* (Etienne Kallos, 2018). All other South African films with comparable scope were considered, but not analysed in detail. Films with historical narratives and not addressing masculinity or the key themes identified in Chapter 1 were excluded. All contemporary literature about these films, both formal scholarship and media reports, was studied and analytically compared to my readings of the core set of films. These films are theorised in their milieu of sweeping sociopolitical changes in South Africa. Additional insights were gained from interviews with Helen Kuun, distributor of *Inxeba* and *Die Stropers* in South Africa, and the directors of both films, John Trengove and Etienne Kallos.

The goal is to examine whether these films contribute to contemporary debates on masculinity and sexuality in South Africa. Through examination of representations of masculinity and sexuality in post-apartheid queer films, as well as investigation of the problems some of these films encountered during their production, distribution and reception stages, this study investigates how the so-called 'crisis of masculinity' manifested itself in post-apartheid South African society.

Chapter 1: AFRICAN QUEER CINEMA

1.1 Review

In the 1990s a wave of political, social and religious homophobia swept across Africa. Its unexpected consequence was the stimulation of a pan-African gay rights movement, previously most evident on the continent as part of the anti-apartheid struggle in South Africa and in the struggle diaspora. This activism gave rise to gay-friendly creative arts, including the production of three films from Guinea, Côte d'Ivoire and South Africa which broke the mould (Epprecht 2011) and lay the foundation for a new pan-African cinematic movement which explores queer subcultures and upon which identities are being built (Botha 2014). A small but growing number of courageous artists and filmmakers started exposing Africa's diverse sexualities to the world with narratives and characters that wield powerful critiques both of contemporary African society and of Western prescriptions for Africa (Epprecht 2008). This notion of a 'restorative queer aesthetic' (Boehmer 2005, p.126) coincided with a similar movement in African literature.

The film *Dakan (Destiny)* (Mohamed Camara, 1997) features the first-ever on-screen kiss by two African men (Epprecht 2013b) and what Matthew Krouse (2006) would describe as 'the most sexually explicit opening scene in African cinema' (p.12). *Woubi Chéri* (Laurent Bocahut and Philip Brooks, 1998) was the first of a series of documentaries drawing from new research by historians and anthropologists which gave African homosexuals a voice, allowing them to describe their world in their own words for the first time (Krouse 2006; Epprecht 2008). The documentary *The Man Who Drove With Mandela* (Greta Schiller, 1998) shows how queer identities constituted an indelible part of the struggle for racial equality in South Africa (Peach 2007; Botha 2014). The film implies that the close friendship between the African National Congress (ANC) leadership and the film's subject, Cecil Williams, was one of the main reasons for the ANC's subsequent pro-queer stance (Hoad et al. 2005).

These examples do not preclude the existence of queer cinema in Africa before the 1990s. The films of Senegalese filmmaker Djibril Diop Mambéty, especially his gender-fluid characterisations in *Touki Bouki* (1973), are evidence that there is more to discover if we allow ourselves to examine subjects from outside political discourses. Mambéty, one of the fathers of African cinema and arguably its most talented director, was ‘certainly its most counter-hegemonic’ (Harrow 2001, p.76). Three films which deal overtly with same-sex sexuality were produced in South Africa during the apartheid era, all three in the year 1988: *Quest for Love* (Helena Nogueira), *The Shadowed Mind* (Cedric Sundstrom) and *The Soldier* (Matthew Krouse). However, there are several examples of South African films warranting queer readings dating back to the first Afrikaans sound film, *Sarie Marais* (Joseph Albrecht, 1931), and *Zonk!* (Hyman Kirstein, 1950) (Botha 2007; Maingard 2003; Peach 2007).

Nigeria’s video-film production industry offers the most extensive collection of African same-sex representations (Ukadike 2014; Osinubi 2019a). However, categorising these Nollywood films as queer requires qualification as they certainly do not celebrate queerness (Green-Simms 2018). Nollywood films are generally homophobic, moralistic melodramas filled with twenty-first century Pentecostal evangelism and demonising gay and lesbian characters (Epprecht 2011; Green-Simms 2012). But the mere existence of Nollywood films depicting homosexuality indicates that a receptive audience has emerged, while ‘a wider awareness of same-sex sexuality in Nigeria and in Africa’ is created (Epprecht 2008; Osinubi 2019a, p.335).

South Africa’s history of queer activism is ‘unique’ within Africa, not only because queer voices in the media under apartheid were silenced due to their resistance to the oppressive system, but also because of the present-day conflicting coexistence of constitutional protection and homophobic violence (Botha 2007, p.66; Osinubi 2019a, p.335). Gay rights groups in South Africa were buoyed by future president Thabo Mbeki’s explicit promise in 1987 that the ANC would combat homophobia along with all other forms of discrimination in a future democratic South Africa (Tatchell 2005). Queer identities defied the fixed categories of race, ethnicity, class, gender and sexuality imposed on South Africans by the apartheid system (Botha 2016). This set the

stage for film and literature which aimed to counter 'crippling stereotypes of hegemonic masculinity and anti-racism conventions' (Epprecht 2011, p.154).

The twenty-first century spawned a vast collection of portrayals of queer lives in South African documentary and feature films. The films are linked to the country's history of colonialism, apartheid and, more recently, post-apartheid life and 'the supposed incompatibility of homosexuality with African cultural values' (Osinubi 2019a, p.340). Sexuality has become one of the foremost political questions in post-apartheid cinema. The institutionalisation of women's and gay rights placed questions of sexuality and gender firmly on the agenda for South African filmmakers who argued for a radical approach (Balseiro and Masilela 2003). Scholars called for portrayals of black sexuality and gender to be released 'from colonial, apartheid and patriarchal imaginaries' and prioritised towards shaping the course of a new South Africa (Magogodi 2003). The controversial Xhosa film *Inxeba* is a fine example. The documentary *Difficult Love* (Zanele Muholi and Peter Goldsmid, 2010) also fits into this 'radical' category. Muholi is an outspoken photographer and artist-activist with a personal mission to rewrite and document a visual history of black queer, trans and gender-nonconforming people in South Africa (Mason 2018).

The transition to democracy signalled a move away from racial politics in South African film criticism. Kgafela oa Magogodi (2003) was probably one of the first scholars to rather consider the politics of sexuality (Balseiro and Masilela 2003). Through his readings of *Mapantsula* (Oliver Schmitz, 1988) and *Fools* (Ramadan Suleman, 1997), Magogodi called for questions of sexuality to be addressed by filmmakers (2003). Jordache Ellapen (2018) analysed the representation of black African stereotypes in two post-apartheid films, *Tsotsi* (Gavin Hood, 2005) and *The Wooden Camera* (Ntshavheni wa Luruli, 2003); while Nicky Falkof (2016) brought together questions of cinema, homosexuality, masculinity and whiteness through an analysis of *Skoonheid* and *Sleeper's Wake* (Barry Berk, 2012). The subject is not without controversy, exemplified by the outrage surrounding the 2018 release of *Inxeba*. This film was at first classified as pornography, then banned, thereafter unbanned, and when eventually released, some cinema managers were too frightened to screen it after

receiving death threats (Levitt 2018; Roets 2018; SABC News 2018). Anele Siswana and Peace Kiguwa's (2018) investigation of social media representations of masculinity in *Inxeba* argues that despite the brouhaha, the film created a space for consideration of alternative masculinities and sexualities.

1.2 Key Themes

Two central themes in post-apartheid cinema are demands for 'an authentic representation of black African identity' and, in particular, for black African masculinity (Ellapen 2018, p.240). Morrell (2001) suggests masculinities in southern Africa not only reflect the past, but have also been *the cause of* that turbulent past (p.12). Films dealing with subjects such as masculinity are part of a growing list of cinemas 'that engage[s] with issues beyond apartheid' (Falkof 2016, p.16). According to Helen Nabasuta Mugambi (2007), the conditions for masculinity within a contemporary African framework require urgent theorisation, she asserts that in Africa 'a difficult gender discourse exists, whether or not academics choose to engage with it' (p.294).

The liberalisation of sexuality in South Africa is accompanied by increasing sexual violence (Walker 2005), another key theme. Thokozani Xaba (2001) sees the rise in violent crime, especially by young men going on the rampage—robbing, killing, raping—as a direct response to the crisis of masculinity which arose with the transition from apartheid to democracy. Researchers focus mainly on black South African men, investigating principally how they are influenced by African-American models of masculinity (Haupt 2008) and how crime and violence are a manifestation of anti-apartheid struggle masculinities (Walker 2005). Statistics indicate disproportionately high rates of rape and homophobic violence in South Africa, especially rape of black lesbians in deprived communities (Fletcher 2016; Mendos 2019), an atrocity known as 'corrective rape.'

Unsurprisingly, much recent scholarship has focused on contesting this ‘homosexuality as an “un-African” perversion’ myth (Reid 2006, p.14), perpetuated since the 1990s, with the most vociferous proponents being politicians and clergy from across Africa (Botha 2016; Epprecht 2013a; Green-Simms 2018; Hoad 2007; Livermon 2018; Osinubi 2018, Reid 2013). Scholarship supporting the myth gave African leaders ‘apparent scientific credibility’ when extolling the importance of ‘African values as a means to combat homosexuality [...] as somewhat deviant and un-African behaviors’ (Epprecht 2008, p.132).

The controversy surrounding the ‘homosexuality as un-African’ myth—a fourth key theme of contemporary queer cinema in Africa—escalated in 1995 when then Zimbabwean president Robert Mugabe banned the organisation GALZ (Gay and Lesbians of Zimbabwe) from the Zimbabwe International Book Fair (Epprecht 2008). At its opening, Mugabe denounced homosexuals as ‘sodomists’ and ‘sexual perverts’ (Hoad 2007, p. xi). A few days later at a Heroes Day rally in Harare, Mugabe upped the ante: ‘If dogs and pigs don’t do it, why must human beings? [...] We have our own culture and we must rededicate ourselves to our traditional values that make us human beings’ (Hoad 2007, p.xi; Gevisser 2005; Reid 2013). The timing of Mugabe’s intervention was significant. On the one hand his pronouncements were attempts at deflecting attention from his own failings as an autocrat who ruined the Zimbabwean economy, on the other, ‘homosexuals were merely a convenient scapegoat for the failures of decolonization’ (Hoad 2007, p.xii).

The representation of homosexuality in conjunction with topics considered taboo or culturally sensitive—a final theme—is situated within a deeply divisive social and academic discourse, as illustrated by the recent controversy over the film *Inxeba*. Current studies are mainly situated within African literary studies and predominantly conducted by scholars based outside Africa, especially North America and Europe, as a result of what Osinubi (2018) calls ‘the complicity of African universities in denouncing LGBTQ communities’ (p.597).

For Alexie Tcheuyap (2005) representations of homosexuality in African cinema marks a 'moral decline,' which he lumps with pornography and claims to be part of 'the radical cultural metamorphosis' experienced by African societies since independence (pp.143–154). Tcheuyap additionally considers African societies as homophobic 'because they nurture their traditional values' and see homosexuality as a threat. He apportions blame also to filmmakers, proclaiming that the integration of films that offer representations of homosexuality into the African cultural realm is problematic since it challenges the father of African cinema, Ousmane Sembène's, concept of political and cultural transformation.

Chapter 2: *INXEBA (THE WOUND)*

The Wound was born out of a desire to push back against certain clichéd stereotypes of black masculinity perpetuated inside and outside African cinema.

— John Trengove 2018a, p.9

2.1 The Film

John Trengove's *Inxeba* (2017) is South Africa's most acclaimed film to date,¹ yet simultaneously its most controversial. At the core of this controversy lies the film's central theme: the practice of *ulwaluko*, a closely guarded Xhosa rite of passage. Amongst others, the *ulwaluko* ritual entails the circumcision of boys aged eighteen years and older, known as *umkwetha* (initiates), followed by their separation from society for up to six weeks. During this period of seclusion, they are guarded and cared for by a designated, individual caregiver who guides the boys through the process of achieving *indoda* (manhood) (Ntombana 2011; Mfecane 2016).

Inxeba tells the story of Xolani, a factory worker, who joins the men of his community to initiate a group of teenage boys. Xolani is appointed the guardian of Kwanda, a defiant queer initiate from the city, who discovers that Xolani is in a secret relationship with another caregiver, Vija. Xolani's relationship with Vija, who has a wife and children, is consummated only once a year when they meet up during *ulwaluko*.

No South African film before has sparked such heated public debate, laying bare deep-rooted social divisions in response to queer sexualities, regardless of existing legal and constitutional sanction thereof. The mere fact that *Inxeba* contains an approximate

¹ *Inxeba* won 26 international awards and shortlisted for the 90th Academy Awards Best Foreign Language Film category.

depiction of the *ulwaluko* ritual and that somehow this could have any proximity to homosexuality was enough to stir up controversy. Trengove, Nakhane Touré (lead actor),² Elias Riberio (producer) and Batana Vundla (co-producer) publicly identify as queer, a fact which did not go unnoticed by the film's detractors (Siswana and Kiguwa 2018; Trengove 2018c). Furthermore, *Inxeba* calls urgent attention to the discourse on African masculinities, the 'un-African' myth, cultural appropriation and the right of representation of traditions.

2.2 A Timeline of Controversy

Nakhane—who himself underwent the initiation process—claims the controversy started soon after the film's international premiere at the Sundance Film Festival in 2017. Nakhane explains that South Africans jumped to conclusions after viewing a two-minute trailer which appeared online in March 2017, thinking the film was an exposé of sacred rituals and disrespectful of Xhosa culture (Trengove and Touré 2018). The reaction was not unexpected. '*Ulwaluko* is a taboo ritual and representing it in the way we have is contentious, we knew from the start that we would spark strong reactions from traditionalists,' said Trengove (2018b, p.12). Subsequent international film festival screenings and continuous reports of acclaim appearing in the South African media fuelled a growing hostile response to the film. Nakhane started receiving death threats because he 'disrespected Xhosa tradition by exposing the intricacies of initiation' (Siswana and Kiguwa 2018, p.58).

In July 2017, prior to its South African premiere at the Durban International Film Festival, the Film and Publication Board (FPB)—South Africa's official content-classification authority—granted *Inxeba* a 16LS rating: meaning that the film was unsuitable for persons under the age of sixteen with additional warnings that the film contained the 'use of bad language' and 'scenes involving sexual conduct and sexual

² Since the release of *Inxeba*, Nakhane—also an accomplished musician—has dropped the use of his last name (Mokoena 2018; Tracer 2019).

activity' (FPB 2012, p.15). Despite attempts by the Xhosa king to block screenings (Tswana 2017; Chutel 2018a), the film received a limited Oscar-qualifying run in cinemas in Johannesburg and Cape Town in September 2017, after which an Academy Awards vetted panel facilitated by the CEO of the National Film and Video Foundation selected *Inxeba* as South Africa's official entry for the 90th Academy Awards Foreign Language category (Vourlias 2017). A week before the film's scheduled national release on 2 February 2018, the Congress of Traditional Leaders of South Africa (Contralesa) and the Man and Boy Foundation (MBF) appealed to the Commission for the Protection of the Rights of Cultural, Religious and Linguistic Communities for support to block the release. The chairperson of the Commission told them they were 'swimming upstream' if their opposition was 'because of homophobia' and advised their objections instead to be 'about misrepresentation of [the] culture' (Collison 2018).

A day before *Inxeba*'s release, Contralesa and MBF lodged an appeal with the FPB against the 16LS rating. Ten days later, the Appeal Tribunal overturned the original classification, gave the film an X18SNLVP rating—the rating for hardcore pornography with foul language, graphic violence and societal prejudice—and ordered the immediate removal of the film from public circulation (Maasdorp 2018). The reclassification meant that the film was effectively banned since it could not be screened in any commercial cinemas, but only at licensed adult premises such as sex shops (Chutel 2018b, FPB 2018; McKaiser 2018a). Despite ambiguous statements to the contrary (Collison 2018; MBF 2018), the consensus opinion held that appellants and tribunal members were conflating privately held beliefs about homosexuality with the classification criteria (McKaiser 2018a). Contralesa and the National House of Traditional Leaders (NHTL) of South Africa are vocal opponents of same-sex rights, calling same-sex marriages a 'wicked, decadent and immoral Western practice' (Livermon 2015, p.14). In 2012 they called for the removal of LGBTQ rights from the South African constitution (Booyesen et al. 2016).

On 6 March 2018, the Pretoria High Court overturned the X18 with a provisional 18SNL rating, pending a 'thorough review of the Appeal Tribunal's decision' (thewoundthefilm 2018). This meant that the film could be rereleased commercially on 9 March 2018.

The NHTL launched a High Court bid to stop the film from opening on 8 March, but a judge ruled that the public had the right to see the film (Lindeque 2018).

It is necessary to take a closer look at the reasons for reclassification and ‘banning’ of the film, since that provides a departure point for the main themes of this study. The Appeal Tribunal based their ruling on a list of complaints against the film, summarised in a published report (FPB 2018, pp.2–4). These included, amongst others, that *Inxeba*:

- was of no scientific, educational or artistic value throughout;
- misrepresented the traditional initiation practice;
- insulted Xhosa culture and traditions;
- exposed boys ‘prematurely to the adult experience of the passage to manhood’ given that no ‘men’ under the age of eighteen were allowed to be initiated;
- revealed ‘coded language’ used during the initiation practice ‘which is spoken only by initiates at particular places (never in public)’ and therefore ‘against the traditions and customs of the Xhosa tribe.’

The tribunal also stated that the director and lead actor were not South Africans, which is untrue. However, what is claimed by the tribunal to be the appellants’ ‘main argument’ is significant: ‘if one is not from a community which they seek to tell a story about, thy [sic] are bound to misunderstand and misrepresent the practices of such a community and that they may not act in the best interest of that community’ (FPB 2018, p.4). This statement was a direct challenge to the right of representation of the Xhosa by a white director and by some of the producers who were white and foreign, a contentious discourse currently pursued in both the media and academic circles (Bongela 2017; Xaso and Pikoli 2017; Siswana and Kiguwa 2018).

2.3 Right of Representation

Because visual technologies in South Africa have traditionally been controlled by a white minority population, ‘questions related to the rights to representation and who

can claim the right to represent whom, particularly in a post-apartheid context,' have become central to any discussion about cinemas (Ellapen 2018, p.240).

In March 2017, long before any public screenings of *Inxeba* in South Africa, Constitutional Court attorney Lwando Xaso and legal communications officer Zukiswa Pikoli penned a scathing opinion piece, attacking director John Trengove for making the film:

Telling our stories through a white lens ensures the dominance and centrality of whiteness. We don't know Trengrove [sic] or his reasons for making the movie and showing it to a foreign audience. What we do know is that he made a movie on Xhosa initiation that is off limits to him [...] The reality is that people from marginalised groups do not get the luxury of defining their own place in a norm that is profoundly white, straight and often patriarchal [...] Trengrove [sic] had no right to make this movie, never mind that Xhosa people were used as a conduit to tell this story, he should have had the ability to morally regulate himself.

In their investigation of social media representations around the release of the *Inxeba*, Anele Siswana and Peace Kiguwa noted much discussion pointing to 'problematic race dynamics about the director who is a "white" man' and an '*ikwenkwe* (an uncircumcised) or *inja* (a dog) boy' and therefore not allowed to comment on matters to do with initiation (2018, pp.53–61). Siswana and Kiguwa stated that the hostility towards the film needs to be understood within the cultural context from which it had been derived, 'characteristically conservative and rooted in rigid patriarchal traditions that reinforce binary gendered and sexual identifications' (p.56).

Keyan Tomaselli believes that film can dismantle 'notions of race and whiteness' (2006, p.48). Ellapen (2007) suggests that the debate should not centre around race, but rather 'the politicised position held when constructing images, and whether the images reinforce stereotypes which are historically outdated' (p.134). Trengove

(2018a, p.9) was aware of this discourse and of his limitations as a white filmmaker, something he felt compelled to address:

As a white man, representing marginalised black realities that are not my own, the situation is of course complicated. It was important to me that the story mirrors this problem.

Trengove chose the character of Kwanda—an outsider to the traditional world—to express his own ideas about human rights and individual freedom. That Kwanda's rebellious character expresses Trengove's sentiments and position within the 'un-African' discourse is evident throughout the film's dialogue, which Trengove co-wrote. Kwanda tells Xolani, 'This is South Africa, not Uganda or Zimbabwe. We're not led by Mugabe. Like Africa doesn't know gay love? I'm sure Shaka and all his warriors wanted each other' (Trengove 2018a).

Trengove (2018c) was disappointed that instead of *Inxeba* being celebrated as 'a queer film by a queer filmmaker,' discourses around race and tradition dominated the conversation—especially considering statements by former Zimbabwean ruler Robert Mugabe inspired the film in the first place:

Statements that he and other African leaders have made since the early '90s imply that homosexuality is a symptom of western decadence that threatens 'traditional' culture. And so we thought: 'okay, let's use that idea.' Let's imagine 'gayness' as some kind of virus that penetrates and threatens a patriarchal organism, and let's see how that organism responds to being penetrated (Trengove 2018a).

2.4 *Indoda Above All*

When I was sixteen, the regent decided that it was time I become a man. In Xhosa tradition, this is achieved through one means only: circumcision.

— Nelson Mandela 1996, p.14

Recent scholarship suggests that patriarchy is the dominant social order in African, and specifically South African, society (Balseiro and Masilela 2003; Reid and Walker 2005; Reid 2006; Epprecht 2008; Brown 2012; Falkof 2016). Within this patriarchy not all masculinities are equal. Hierarchy plays a central role. According to Raewyn Connell's (1995) seminal model of masculinities, hegemonic masculinity wields the most political, social and cultural power. Men who lay claim to hegemonic masculinity gain much 'power and privilege' from it (Morrell 1998, p.608), it being the most 'honored' way of being a man (Connell and Messerschmidt 2005, p.832). Hegemonic masculinity also relies on the subordination of women and young, effeminate or gay men (Hanke 1992). In contemporary South Africa, hegemonic masculinity 'emphasizes the importance of masculine control, (un)emotionality, physicality and toughness, competition, success, responsibility, and (hetero)sexuality' (Luyt 2003). Despite the country's transition to democracy and a new constitution with new ideals for gender equality (including sexual orientation), men—regardless of their differences—are still regarded more powerful than women.

To understand the *Inxeba* controversy, it is essential to consider the basic principles of Xhosa masculinity and to explore the real reason that sparked the controversy. The dominance of *ulwaluko* in the lives of Xhosa men and its dominant themes of hegemony—expressed through the power of older men and punishment for nonconformity—cannot be understated (Magodyo et al. 2017). Hegemonic masculinity is exclusively heterosexual and, according to Connell, 'not just an idea in the head, or a personal identity,' but a masculinity that merges with 'organised social relations' (1995, p.29). Social relations are considerably meaningful in Xhosa culture.

Sakhumzi Mfecane (2018a), who writes extensively on Xhosa masculinities, claims that gender theories developed in the Global North are embedded in Western epistemologies and therefore offer inadequate accounts of African masculinities. Mfecane advocates for the creation of African-centred theories of masculinity to account for the complex lives of African men. Albeit useful in advancing South African masculinity scholarship globally, the application of Global North theories has unintentionally marginalised the voices of those they study and seek to change (Mfecane 2018b). Mfecane believes that—despite substantial investment from government and NGOs to eradicate gender inequality in South Africa—old theories do not offer solutions to persistent problems such as violence against women, rape and queerphobia: ‘Research and interventions centre on the same goal of subverting patriarchy without putting patriarchy in its proper social and historical context’ (p.11).

Despite apparent parallels, the Xhosa practice of *ulwaluko* and the associated concept of *indoda* represent a version of masculinity which does not conform to established theories of hegemonic masculinity originating from the Global North (Mfecane 2018a). Sexuality presents no barrier regarding the Xhosa initiation process, although it would be fair to say that queer Xhosa men’s desire to conform to societal norms and pressures probably plays a large part in their decision to be traditionally circumcised (Ntozini and Ngqangweni 2016). Heteronormativity is important in defining hegemonic masculinity in South Africa, as evidenced in studies of local and regional social practices where hegemonic masculinity is present (Luyt 2012, p.69). Ingrid Lynch and Matthew Clayton (2016) present substantive evidence that the participation of queer men in the initiation process ‘is a focus on restoring *masculinity*, and not sexuality’ (p.287), although some evidence points to expectations of their families for them to return ‘corrected’ (Lynch and Clayton 2016; Ntozini and Ngqangweni 2016).³

This recent South African scholarship subverts Connell’s (1995) concept of masculinity. The order of masculine hierarchies in the *indoda* discourse is not based on sexual orientation; hegemony is achieved through *ulwaluko* and circumcision status. A Xhosa

³ Talk of correcting or repairing queer sexualities evoke uncomfortable analogies with the sexual violence often directed at lesbians and termed ‘corrective rape.’

man's status 'is grounded primarily in the physical body (penis)' which serves as the medium through which men prove they are a real man, and determines their rank in society (Mfecane 2016, pp.208–210). In Xhosa culture, the circumcised penis is the primary indicator to ensure that the male body conforms to the cultural definition of manhood and perpetuates the hierarchies of men in the community (Ndangam 2009). Traditionally circumcised unmarried Xhosa men are better respected than married men who were medically circumcised (Kometsi 2004; Mavundla et al. 2010; Mfecane 2016). A queer *indoda* would also be ranked above a medically circumcised man. However, because a married man is ranked higher than a bachelor, a queer man who has achieved *indoda* would by implication be ranked lower. Seniority is also calculated by the number of years a man has been an *indoda* (Kometsi 2004).

2.5 The Real Controversy

Why then, given all of the above, did *Inxeba* stir up such controversy? Debates around race, appropriation and representation of traditions are certainly not new in South African or African film discourse. Defenders of the film were quick to claim that the film did not reveal more detail about the circumcision ritual than South African statesman Nelson Mandela's description thereof in his autobiography (1996). Here the crisis of masculinity has less to do with the crisis experienced by all South African men as a result of the transition of gender/power relations expressed in the new constitution, but rather is a result of internal hegemony amongst Xhosa men (Demetriou 2001).

At centre lies a sacred and secret 'coded language' which Contralesa and MBF alluded to in their appeal to curtail the release and distribution of *Inxeba* (FPB 2018). Other than the actual circumcision scar, the initiated have only one other way to prove and defend their manhood: during their seclusion after circumcision, initiates are taught '*isikwetha* (language of the initiates)' (Ntozini and Ngqangweni 2016, p.1310) and 'riddles' (Froneman and Kapp 2017, p.1)—vocabulary used to prove that one has undergone the ritual and used to defend a Xhosa man's manhood when challenged

(Mgqolozana 2009). Initiates must memorise this language, which sets them apart from boys and from men who were circumcised in hospital or not circumcised at all, and through which they gain entrance to ritual spaces such as taverns and meetings to which only *amadoda* (Xhosa men with *indoda*) have access (Kometsi 2004, Mfecane 2016, p.207).

Every source considered for this study discloses the general framework of the *ulwaluko* ritual, but not a single reference reveals any of the secret language. The film, however, does. Director John Trengove divulged that the ritual scenes were filmed in documentary fashion, admitting that much dialogue was improvised (Roxborough 2018). He also filmed with a real community of Xhosa men—not extras—who regularly enact the initiation (Trengove 2018c). In addition, the lead actors are all Xhosa men who had undergone *ulwaluko*. The film contains several scenes not subtitled into English, especially dialogue of initiates and caregivers. Do the men—perhaps inadvertently—use some of the coded language? The FPB Appeal Tribunal and the final High Court decision indeed suggest so, the latter which dismissed the tribunal’s ruling only on grounds of jurisdiction and procedure (FPB 2018; Columbia Global Freedom of Expression 2018).

High Court Judge Joseph Raulinga’s ruling concerned itself with ‘the balancing of two parallel equations, which are by all means not always equal—the right to cultural rights and the right to freedom of expression—the need to balance the right to freedom of expression and cultural rights’ (Columbia Global Freedom of Expression 2018, p.12). Despite ruling in favour of the distributors, Raulinga suggested that the film was indeed harmful, disturbing, and broke cultural taboos: ‘Initiation or circumcision is strongly believed to be sacred not only by the amaXhosa, but by the majority of African people in South Africa and elsewhere in other African countries’ (p.13). The ‘problematic language’ contained in the ruling is internationally regarded significant because cultural rights—beliefs and practices—enjoy increased protection and could ‘limit the distribution of films that may potentially offend certain communities or traditions’ (Columbia Global Freedom of Expression 2018).

2.6 Masculinity and Violence

Threats of violence against the film cast and crew, distributors and cinema staff expose a troubling aspect of the controversy surrounding *Inxeba*, in contrast to a fundamental principle of international law ‘that the right to freedom of expression embraces expression that may be regarded as “deeply offensive”’ (Columbia Global Freedom of Expression 2018). Violence could prevail over protection of cultural rights, as shown by the inability of Contralesa and MBF and their supporters on social media to distance themselves from these threats of violence. Post-apartheid studies point to masculinity and violence being interconnected and suggest that hegemonic masculinity may not *prefer* violence to exert power, but reacts variously to change, from accepting and supporting new sexual paradigms to fiercely defending an existing way of life (Morrell 2001; Xaba 2001; Posel 2003, 2005; Niehaus 2005). Integration resulting from social transformation may lead to acceptance of sexual minorities, but is often accompanied by brutal violence (Reid and Walker 2005).

Although questions of race, tradition and sexuality dominated the controversy around *Inxeba*, little attention was given to the film’s ending. I consider the ending as the central and arguably most divisive scene of the film. Xolani, the queer caregiver, desperate to protect his secret, and by implication the secrets of *ulwaluko*, murders the openly gay Kwanda by pushing him off a cliff. ‘You can’t speak of what’s happened on the mountain,’ says Xolani (Figure 1).

Xolani and Kwanda at the edge of a cliff in *Inxeba*.

The film's ending is ambiguous. An obvious explanation is that *amadoda* are prepared to protect their secrets with brutal force—regardless of their sexuality. The use of violence to retain power and secrecy to build a masculine identity has been emphasised by many studies.⁴ Deborah Posel (2005) theorises that secrecy is a way of preventing public censure, a means to avoid the shame and stigma which exposure may bring, whilst traditional leaders who defend *ulwaluko* would maintain it is merely to ensure its sacredness (Ndangam 2009). Violent acts aim to (re-)establish order and enforce hegemonic male power (Msibi 2009; Livermon 2018).

The ending may be interpreted entirely differently when taking direction from Martin Mhando (2014), who bemoans the fact that we continue 'to apply Anglo-American perspectives and cinematic discourses in trying to understand African paradigms and sociological conditions' (p.18). Instead the ending can be considered an example of the direction in which Mhando suggests African cinema should proceed, one which reflects the ambiguities inscribed in the language of cinema as it relates to Africa and one which pays attention to the cultural significances embedded in the text.

Xolani and Vija's relationship is complex and does not conform to fixed Western homosexual identities, a ritual with its own signs and signals, which manifests itself annually at the foot of a waterfall (Figure 2). Here, the noise of the water drowns out the rest of the world, clearly suggested by the opening shot of the film, which is of the top of the waterfall (Figure 3). In a single continuous shot, the camera pans down the waterfall to where the water crashes into the plunge pool. The camera descends underwater and the opening credits appear over an almost black underwater sequence with only the muffled sound of the waterfall audible. The diegetic sound of water merges with an industrial whine, and as the camera pops out from under the water to reveal the waterfall again, there is an abrupt cut to a tracking shot of Xolani driving a forklift, wearing earmuffs, drowning out the noise of his workplace (Figure 4). We have

⁴ See studies by Kgamadi Kometsi 2004; Sakhumzi Mfecane 2016, 2018b; Ingrid Lynch and Matthew Clayton 2017; Tapiwa Magodyo et al. 2017)

just been privy to his foremost thoughts, thinking about the space he was about to escape to.

Figure 2
Xolani and Vija in the plunge pool at the bottom of the waterfall in *Inxeba*.

Figure 3
The opening shot of the film *Inxeba*, the top of the waterfall.

Figure 4
A tracking shot of Xolani driving a forklift in *Inxeba*.

At the waterfall, Xolani and Vija created their own personal queer space, which only exists within the confines of the 'mountain' (Figure 5). Flair Donglai Shi (2018) believes

that the murder of Kwanda can ‘be regarded as Xolani’s rejection of Western middle-class gay values and allows the film to shift the audience’s identification back to Xolani and make them reflect on his (and their own) positionality.’ Shi’s review of the film is one of few which attempts to theorise the ending, and also one which Trengove says ‘gets what I was going for and also our shortcomings in terms of getting there’ (J Trengove 2019, personal communication, 28 June).

Xolani and Vija intimately embracing at the foot of the waterfall in *Inxeba*.

Kgamadi Kometsi (2004) is concerned that the lack of attention accorded to queer sexual identities amongst the Xhosa illustrates ‘that it is an invalid, nonexistent identity’ (p.57). Kometsi submits that queer masculinities are not always silenced through overtly violent behaviour. Silence and secrecy may suggest that queer people are generally accepted in the ambit of *ulwaluko*. However, as Posel (2005) found, ‘denial and silence are associated with cultural, political and psychic logics of shame and stigma’ (p.41). The fact that queer sexualities are wilfully ignored also comprises a form of violence, one which K. Sello Duiker referred to as ‘the quiet violence’ (Kometsi 2004, p.57; Carolin and Frenkel 2013). Such denial of queer sexualities, which includes stigmatisation, silencing and alienation of same-sex behaviour, has real social consequences. The general discourse of denial also feeds into the ‘un-African’ debate, which in turn fuels violence against queer people.

Tiawo Osinubi’s (2019b) reflections on Wanuri Kahiu’s Kenyan film *Rafiki* (2018) and on recent trends in African queer cinema make specific reference to *Inxeba*. He points to the fact that *Inxeba* pivots on crucial scenes of dialogue which deliberately includes

situated declarations, i.e. dialogue which taps into the discourse on queer rights in Africa and deliberately inserts queer subjects into African cinemas. Such scenes, often within sites of caregiving, become a vantage point from which to critique all manners of social behaviour. Trengove therefore, through Kwanda's character, powerfully appeals against homophobia.

Chapter 3: *WHILE YOU WEREN'T LOOKING*

[...] black lesbian women are still refused entry into the nation's most public spaces and are punished for their same-sex desires and relationships.

— Zanele Muholi 2004, p.117

3.1 The Film

Osinubi (2019a) singles out Catherine Stewart's *While You Weren't Looking* (2015) as a significant African queer film for exposing the social realities of the post-apartheid class divide and as another example of a film which taps directly into the discourse on queer rights in Africa by deliberately inserting queer subjects into African cinema (p.340). Osinubi highlights the fact that the film raises the subject of sexual violence against lesbians in townships, another manifestation of post-apartheid masculinity-in-crisis.

While You Weren't Looking is a post-apartheid melodrama that combines two main narratives: the problems encountered by Dez and Terri, a mixed-race lesbian couple, after twenty-years of marriage, and the sexual awakening and relationships of their eighteen-year-old adopted daughter, Asanda.⁵ At first glance, the film does not distinguish itself as an obvious candidate to examine how queer cinema challenges African notions of masculinity. However, by exploring Asanda's sexuality through a relationship with Shado, a tommy boy from Cape Town's Khayelitsha township, and invoking the art and activism of Zanele Muholi, the film engages publicly with one of the most controversial disquisitions about post-apartheid South Africa, that of sexual violence. Tommy boys are women who assume masculine behaviours and dress codes and often don't identify as lesbians 'as they feel more like men than women' (Morgan and Wieringa 2005, p.318).

⁵ The film's original cut contained a third narrative dealing with the ageing academic Mack's search for a long-lost lover and freedom fighter whom he sheltered during the apartheid years.

3.2 Sexual Violence

Amanda Swarr (2012) suggests that butch lesbians risk physical and sexual violence because they challenge and subvert notions of masculinity by being both unavailable and threatening to heterosexual men. These women are seen as competition for straight women's affections and are themselves sexually inaccessible, threatening, and 'breaking the rules of heterosexuality' (p.979). As such, the (female) character Shado's masculine appearance and behaviour challenge traditionally normative constructions of gender and expose her and her loved ones to sexual violence—more specifically: corrective rape (Livermon 2018).

Sexual violence is rampant in South Africa. Recent annual crime statistics released by the South African Police Service (2018) indicate 40,035 recorded cases of rape, an average of 110 per day (pp.74–79). Approximately 93% of the rape victims were female, but the official figures are not broken down by sexuality. However, the human rights organisation ActionAid presented evidence that lesbians report at least ten cases of rape per week to a single LGBTQ support group in Cape Town (Martin et al. 2009, p.8).

Corrective rape—also known as curative rape—is a term coined in the 2000s by human rights organisations and NGOs to describe punitive sexual acts in which heterosexual men rape lesbian women in order to 'correct' or 'cure' their homosexuality (Martin et al. 2009; Brown 2012; Swarr 2012; Reyes 2013).⁶ The subject made international headlines when Eudy Simelane, a member of the South African women's football team, was raped and murdered during a period of intense media scrutiny prior to South Africa hosting the 2010 FIFA World Cup (Kelly 2009; Nath 2009). Corrective rape is chronically underreported by the South African media (Van der Schyff 2018).⁷

⁶ The problem is not unique to South Africa, with recent reports of corrective rape from Jamaica, Uganda and Zimbabwe. The term's use has broadened to describe the rape of any member of any sexual minority in order to 'correct' them (Brown 2012, p.46).

⁷ Corrective rape is not classified as a hate crime, or recognised as an entity by the judiciary, or included in the South African Sexual Offences Act (Van der Schyff 2018).

3.3 Shado and the Shadow of Corrective Rape

Through the character of Shado, *While You Weren't Looking* explores the marginalisation of black lesbians living in townships and the threat of sexual violence they face daily. Shado self-identifies as a tommy boy, wears a fedora, 'packs' (stuffs her trousers to create the impression of having a penis) and binds her breasts in order to look more manlike (Figure 6). Her appearance evokes images of American film gangsters. Ellapen (2018) recognises the trope of the gangster figure as a common stereotype in post-apartheid films such as *Tsotsi* (2005) and *The Wooden Camera* (2003), used to imagine and locate dangerous and deviant black African masculinities in the township space.

Shado stuffing her trousers with a rolled bandage ('packing') in *While You Weren't Looking*.

The first exchange of dialogue in the film is between Asanda and Mack, her university lecturer, during a class on gender politics. Mack projects photographs by visual artists Jean Brundrit and Zanele Muholi in a lecture hall (Figures 7–8). He explains that the images 'challenge the binaries of sexuality' and then refers to the moment in August 2009 when the Minister of Arts and Culture refused to open an exhibition celebrating Women's Day, denouncing Muholi's work on show as 'pornographic' [sic] and contrary to the ministry's primary aim of promoting social cohesion and nation-building (Msibi 2011; Matebeni 2013; Thomas 2013).

Photograph by Jean Brundrit in *While You Weren't Looking*.

Detail of Zanele Mhloni's 'Being' (2010) in *While You Weren't Looking*.

Mack poses a question to the students: 'What are the implications of the minister's statement according to gender theory?' Asanda responds: 'That the nation is heterosexual,' which is, of course, one of the central claims at the heart of African queer discourses—that Africa is heterosexual and that homosexuality is un-African. Aidan Prinsloo (2011) suggests that positioning of homosexuality as a threat to traditional masculinity (and femininity) negates homosexuality and sanctions corrective rape as a legitimate practice to reinforce masculinity and traditional gender concepts.

The film explores the un-African myth visibly through the way people react towards Shado's character, underlining how modern queer identities, such as tommy boys, arose in opposition to a general discourse of denial. As highlighted in the *Inxeba*

chapter, the denial of queer sexualities exerts real social consequences which tap into the un-African debate and in turn fuel violence against queer people. *While You Weren't Looking* illustrates the social consequences of such denial on people such as Shado, who struggle with their queer identities: their social stigmatisation, silencing and alienation, as described by Kometsi (2004) in his examination of the emotional upheavals evident in queer sexualities within the Xhosa circumcision tradition.

Although this sequence and subsequent lecture hall sequences indicate clear intention by the film to engage politically and raise issues mostly considered taboo, the film ultimately neglects to deliver on its academic potential by failing to constitute a meaningful critical intervention.

Shado's cousin, Babalo, expresses concern for her safety in the township. 'Stop walking around in the township the way you do. You'll get hurt.' When Shado visits Asanda at home for the first time, she is confronted by the maid Beauty, who tells Shado: 'You are not the same as these people.' Despite both being Xhosa and from the same township, Beauty makes her derision of Shado's lifestyle clear in a conversation with Terri: 'That girl, trouble!' When Terri questions the statement, Beauty explains: 'I know girls like that in the township and the things they do. It's not our culture!' Terri's response points out the obvious: 'But Beauty, we live like that?' Beauty's reply could not be more damning: 'But you're different.' Beauty is reminding Terri of the class and racial divides between Terri and herself and that she does not consider Terri an African.

Swarr (2012), who has studied gender liminality in queer communities in the Global South since 1997, claims that while black South African lesbians demonstrate characteristics of male masculinities by claiming masculine privileges, 'they are not simply copying men, but creating masculinities' (p.967). Women such as Shado challenge notions that women must be feminine 'and that only people with male bodies can strongly express masculinities' (p.968). These women transcend mere imitation of men, but rather redefine what it is to be masculine.

While You Weren't Looking is a milestone, at the very least attempting to make visible what has remained mostly invisible and contributing to the ongoing struggle to create a safer environment for queer people in South Africa (Osinubi 2019a).

3.4 Zanele Muholi

Photography is not a hobby to me, photography is about politics.

— Zanele Muholi 2014a

I photograph different LGBTI individuals, risking my life, challenging the myth that says being gay, being trans, is un-African [...] A simple image of a queer being in space, that's political.

— Zanele Muholi 2018

Several post-apartheid short films also explored the subjects of corrective rape and masculinity and could be considered companion pieces to *While You Weren't Looking*. Most successful are the films of the photographer and self-proclaimed visual activist Zanele Muholi (Bissonauth 2014; Imma 2017). Their shadow looms large over *While You Weren't Looking*, much larger than the film's central narrative.⁸ The film's intertextuality with Muholi's photographs and films is profound. Some scenes look as if they could have been composed and shot by Muholi herself (Figures 9–10). This is no coincidence, since Muholi's first film, *Enraged by a Picture* (2005), was workshopped and produced by the same team who created *While You Weren't Looking*, the *Out in Africa Gay & Lesbian Film Festival* and its founder and director, Nodi Murphy.⁹

⁸ Muholi ungendered some time in 2018 and now prefers the gender pronouns 'they-them-their' (Berger 2018; Gevisser 2018).

⁹ The *Out in Africa Gay & Lesbian Film Festival* was Africa's first queer film festival (Botha 2003), running from 1994–2018.

'Being' (2007), a triptych by Zanele Muholi.

A scene from *While You Weren't Looking* which resembles Zanele Muholi's photographs in Figure 9.

Muholi is the subject of a growing body of scholarship. They have dedicated their life to documenting victims of sexual violence in South Africa and, increasingly, the rest of Africa (Currier and Migraine-George 2016). Muholi (2009; 2014b; 2015) is certainly not ambiguous about their objectives: to record and make visible the lives of black queer people in South Africa. Muholi's other films also set out to disrupt or corrupt masculine dominance. *Difficult Love* (2010), co-directed with David Goldsmid, is a biographical journey, a protest against calls for a homogeneous African identity. Muholi counters such calls through making visible the lives of queer people on the continent. Muholi's *Films4Peace* (2013) reimagines one of the many funerals of victims of corrective rape.

Enraged by a Picture features scenes which undoubtedly informed the narrative of the tommy boys in *While You Weren't Looking*. Two of the most iconic scenes in both films show women binding their breasts with bandages, a painful body modification which butch lesbians and tommy boys undertake to flatten their torsos into a manlier form and, as Swarr (2012) discovered, in some cases to prevent their breasts from developing (Figures 11–12). These scenes recall Muholi's famous photograph *ID Crisis* (2003), which appears in both *Enraged by a Picture* and *While You Weren't Looking* (Figures 13–14). In *Enraged by a Picture* it features alongside a photograph of the coach of an all-lesbian Johannesburg football club and one of an unidentified female 'participant'¹⁰ captioned *injonga* (Figure 15). *Injonga* is a Zulu word, a gendered term for the active male partner in homosexual anal intercourse (Gevisser and Cameron 1995; Reid 1997; Cage 2003, Epprecht 2008). The word undermines 'the notion that homosexuality is a Western import, by claiming a specifically African homosexual identity' (Reid 1997, p.114). By appropriating the term to designate a butch lesbian, Muholi even further subverts notions of masculinity by not only challenging male heterosexual stereotypes, but also male homosexuals.

Figure 11

Breast-binding scene in *While You Weren't Looking*.

¹⁰ Muholi insists that the people photographed by them are not 'subjects', but active participants in creating a visual history (Muholi and Goldsmid 2010; Muholi 2018).

Breast-binding scene in *Enraged by a Picture*.

Zanele Muholi's photograph 'ID Crisis' (2003) in *Enraged by a Picture*.

Zanele Muholi's photograph 'ID Crisis' (2003) in *While You Weren't Looking*.

Figure 15
Zanele Muholi's photograph 'injonga' (2003) in *Enraged by a Picture*.

Xolelwa 'Ollie' Nhlabatsi's *Lost in the World* (2015), which screened at queer film festivals worldwide, is another noteworthy short film that deals with corrective rape. This fifteen-minute film tells the story of a police officer, Whitney, who avenges the rape and murder of her girlfriend Palesa. There is no indication in the narrative that Palesa was a victim of corrective rape, nor is it shown. The only source of this notion is the film's marketing and publicity campaign, which seemed contrived and opportunistic by focusing entirely on the topic of corrective rape. Nhlabatsi's ignorance on the subject and apparent victim-blaming during a somewhat unapprised Q&A session after a screening in Johannesburg attest to this (Klein 2016).

But in the same way that *While You Weren't Looking* invokes corrective rape through Muholi, without ever mentioning it by name or depicting it, *Lost in the World's* reticence to be transparent in its intentions strengthens Van der Schyff's (2018) argument of social apathy about the phenomenon. This, in turn, increases the relevance of Muholi's work.

Chapter 4: AFRIKAANS QUEER CINEMA

4.1 The Afrikaner

The position of Afrikaners in South Africa has always been contentious, especially as they are considered the engineers of apartheid. Who they are, and what it means to be an Afrikaner, have been contested since the early eighteenth century (De Klerk 1984; Giliomee 2011). The apparent ethnic and racial homogeneity of the Afrikaner was ideologically created amongst white Afrikaans-speakers and reproduced through careful policing of boundaries (Blaser and Van der Westhuizen 2012). In effect, the Afrikaner invented himself as a homogeneous group (Cloete 1992).¹¹

Uriel Abulof (2015) describes the Afrikaner as a modern imagined community whose identity is 'deeply embedded in the territory where it developed' (p.227), but also as 'an ethnic nation with an exceptional sense of collective fragility' (p.6) that has held its existence under threat through fear of 'Anglophone assimilation and non-white assault' (p.13). Subsequently, the perceived existential threat to both their physical and political survival after the end of minority rule in 1994 engulfed the Afrikaners in a crisis of identity (De Klerk 1984; Davies 2009; Giliomee 2011; Verwey and Quayle 2012). The collapse of apartheid exposed the spurious homogeneity of Afrikaners with some embracing the new democratic order while others rejected it (Swart 2001). As a result, class and race have become the determining factors of Afrikaner identity—rather than ethnic affiliation (Davies 2012).

¹¹ Elsie Cloete (1992) points out that 'Afrikaner' as a concept is masculine. A grammatical rule determines that, in Afrikaans, all concepts are masculine and should be signified by the pronouns 'his' and 'him' (p.46).

4.2 Afrikaner Masculinity

For decades, hegemonic Afrikaner masculinity dominated a South African society which was home to multiple definitions of masculinity. Not only culturally dominant, Afrikaners moreover marginalised other masculinities and the gender order as a whole (Morrell 1998; Swart 2001). Kobus du Pisani (2001) explains that Afrikaner masculinity was puritan, with a strict Calvinistic worldview. Religious ideology supported the notion of the Afrikaner as a 'chosen race'. According to Kennedy Owino (2018), this belief also established and reinforced a power hegemony around Afrikaner men, whose masculine ideals manifested in a form of nationalism which was not only racist and militaristic, but 'authoritarian, unforgiving, and unapologetic' (p.158). Beyond its foundation in religion, the ideal[ised] affirmations of masculinity 'were to be found on the rugby field and in the military' (Sonnekus 2013, p.24). Compulsory military service was 'the primary constitutive act of masculinity and citizenship in white South African society' (Conway 2008, p.422).

Necessarily, homosexuality was anathema to such a society. To maintain hegemonic power, the government had to counter threats of the 'other' on two fronts: the external threat presented by 'nonwhites' (countered with apartheid legislation) and the internal threat of white male homosexuality (suppressed through criminalisation, isolation and a conspiracy of silence) (Du Pisani 2001, p.169). The only way queer Afrikaners could hence be true to their own identity was by contesting heteronormativity, which according to Marius Crous (2006) made 'crisis and a state of being in a crisis' the central supposition of debate about Afrikaner queer identity (p.55).

4.3 Afrikaans Queer Cinema

Through their dismantling of apartheid and embracing of neoliberalism, the Afrikaner has been rehabilitated globally (Van der Westhuizen 2007; Davies 2009). The new

millennium brought with it a sentiment that Afrikaans was an endangered language, which in turn led to an upsurge in the Afrikaans arts, culture and media industries (Blaser and Van der Westhuizen 2012; Du Plessis 2012). This cultural explosion was soon accompanied by the globalisation of Afrikaans music and literature,¹² and increasingly also of its cinema.

Chris Broodryk (2015) claims that Afrikaans cinema finds critical engagement in a multicultural society problematic and has hitherto failed to come to terms with its history and politics. Despite this, a select group of Afrikaans feature films recently received festival accolades which lead to international distribution. All these films place numerous aspects of the ideal[ised] Afrikaner masculinity under the microscope. More significantly, the films are all queer: *Skoonheid*; *Die Stropers*; and *Johnny is nie dood nie* (*Johnny is not dead*) (2016) and *Kanarie* (*Canary*) (2018), both by Christiaan Olwagen. Considering that homosexuality had been virtually nonexistent in South African cinema until 1985 (Botha 2016), this is a significant turnaround.

Although queer cinema, I do not examine the two films by Christiaan Olwagen in full. Both films are set in the decade before South Africa's transition to democracy and against the backdrop of involuntary military conscription, one of the most controversial facets of apartheid-era South Africa. Although compulsory military service in the South African Defence Force (SADF) was an essential demonstration of true manhood for young white men (Conway 2004), these films include examinations of historical state oppression whereas this study focuses on sexuality and masculinities post-apartheid.

Homosexuality in the military during apartheid begs further investigation, since two of the directors whose films are discussed in this study are continuing with the military theme for their next projects. Oliver Hermanus's latest film, *Moffie* (2019), which explores how masculinity was shaped and homosexuality rejected through military

¹² Afrikaans hip-hop group 'Die Antwoord' (*The Answer*) is internationally acclaimed; translations of novels by Marlene van Niekerk, Ingrid Winterbach, Deon Meyer and other Afrikaans authors regularly feature on international bestseller lists (Snyckers 2012; Attridge 2014; Chruszczewska 2015; Friedman 2015).

conscription, will receive its world premiere at the 2019 Venice Film Festival (Skinner 2019). Objectors to military conscription were positioned as sexual deviants and *moffies* (faggots) in an attempt to discount any political principles they held (Manion 2006; Conway 2012).¹³ John Trengove is presently casting his next film, *Die Reuk van Appels* (*The Smell of Apples*) (J Trengove 2019, personal communication, 26 June), an adaptation of Mark Behr's 1993 novel about a young boy who witnesses his father—a general in the SADF—raping the boy's best friend.

4.4 *Scoonheid* (*Beauty*)

In her recent study of masculinity in South Africa, Falkof (2016) claims that the most compelling contemporary research on masculinities bypasses white men. *Scoonheid* takes South African cinema in an entirely new direction which, according to Falkof, is 'part of an emerging lexicon of South African cinema that engages with issues beyond apartheid' (p.15).¹⁴ *Scoonheid* has also been the subject of significant scholarship for its ground-breaking look at queer sexual politics, in addition to its challenging exploration of masculinity in post-apartheid South Africa (Falkof 2016; Green-Simms 2018; Siswana and Kiguwa 2018; Osinubi 2019a).

Scoonheid tells the story of Francois, a closeted, homophobic and racist forty-something Afrikaner who becomes infatuated with a younger man, Christian—the *beauty* which becomes the object of his affection (Figure 16). Francois is married with children and is the embodiment of hegemonic masculinity prevalent during the apartheid years. However, he is burdened by the internal shame of being homosexual. He only expresses his sexuality with like-minded men who have secret encounters in isolated locations. When confronted with the realities of the new South Africa, Francois

¹³ Evidence was presented during post-apartheid hearings that queer SADF conscripts were subjected to forced aversion therapy in the 1980s, which included electric shocks and 'treatment' with illicit drugs and hormones, besides being subjected to sexual abuse (Manion 2006).

¹⁴ *Scoonheid* was the first Afrikaans film to premiere at the Cannes Film Festival, where it also won the Queer Palm (Sonnekus 2013).

rejects any notion of interracial sex, or sex with *moffies*. This reveals deep divisions amongst queers in South Africa, dispelling any illusion of homogeneity amongst nonnormative sexualities in South Africa.¹⁵ Theo Sonnekus (2013) describes Francois's masculine identity as 'constantly under threat from racial and sexual "Others," who highlight the hypocrisy and constructedness of the outmoded model of patriarchy that he reveres' (p.22). This threat, and the breakdown of white male hegemony in post-apartheid South Africa, leave Francois frustrated and angry, raising the issue of male-male sexual violence (Osinubi 2019a).

Figure 16

Francois and Christian in *Ssoonheid*.

During apartheid, masculinity was constructed within a frame of 'violence, racism, dominance and control' (Conway 2004, p.214). Falkof (2016) points out that 'masculinities and violence have long gone hand in hand in South Africa' (p.24). Whereas the films examined earlier in this study concern black masculinities, *Ssoonheid* exposes the white man's capacity for violence. Francois's character reveals 'the most aggressive stereotypes of Afrikaner masculinity: the white man whose rage at his loss of power leads to violent confrontation, and who believes he has the ultimately right of control over those even less powerful than him' (Falkof 2016, pp.25–26).

¹⁵ Scott Everett Couper's (2018) examination of queer social hierarchies in South Africa is fascinating in this regard.

The threat of sexual violence in *Scoonheid* goes further than in *While You Weren't Looking* when Francois violently rapes Christian in a hotel room after his sexual advances are rejected. Not only some black men in the townships react violently against their economic and political emasculation after the collapse of apartheid. Several studies have concluded that domestic abuse and rape by white men, and homophobia amongst them, have also increased (Du Pisani 2001; Van der Watt 2005; Walker 2005).

Interesting comparisons can be drawn between the masculinities constructed in *Scoonheid*, *While You Weren't Looking* and *Inxeba*. Director John Trengove (2018c) credits *Scoonheid* as the first in a line of 'challenging' queer South African films and suggests that *Inxeba* would not have existed without *Scoonheid*: 'They are both films that speak more about patriarchy or masculinity than being traditional queer films.' Although *Scoonheid* is a queer film, it certainly does not 'celebrate queerness' (Green-Simms 2018, p.657). The same can be said for *Inxeba*. Sonnekus (2013) could have been describing Xolani and Vija's relationship and identity in *Inxeba* when he described the archetypal Afrikaner masculinity demonstrated in *Scoonheid*:

The act of having sex with men, in no way suggests belonging to the gay community or buying into any particular lifestyle. Homosexuality [...] is still treated contemptuously in certain contexts, resulting in acts of expulsion and violence that re-inscribe the stigmas associated with 'faggots' in traditional Afrikaner, heteronormative rhetoric (p.23).

4.5 *Die Stropers (The Harvesters)*

The central narrative of *Die Stropers* pits two teenage boys against each other amid a conservative and deeply religious farming community enveloped by an almost suffocating sense of imminent dread. The farmers live in constant fear of crime, farm murders, affirmative action and the expropriation of their land, which Rebecca Davies

(2009) considers a major contributor to ‘the current sense of crisis among Afrikaners’ (p.110). The very notion of white farmers has always been contentious and politicised, with the subject of land ownership and the brutal and unjust treatment of farmworkers never far removed from public consciousness (Resane 2018).¹⁶ The similarities to John Trengove’s *Inxeba* are profound. Both narratives develop around closeted queer characters within deeply insular and queerphobic communities fighting to protect their ways of life. Equally significant is the depiction of Afrikaner masculinity at a crossroads, which it shares with Oliver Hermanus’ *Skoonheid* (Lodge 2018).

According to Du Pisani (2001), the ideal expression of Afrikaner masculinity was ‘the image of the simple, honest, steadfast, religious and hard-working *boer* (farmer)’ (p.158). On the farms, the traditional family was central to upholding the values of the Afrikaner and, according to Susanne Klausen (2015), ‘first and foremost the site of production of new members of the *volk* (nation)’ with the wife consigned to the role of *volksmoeder* (mother of the nation) (p.62). The Afrikaner wife was expected to defer to her husband and embrace her duty as custodian of the Afrikaner national character (p.63). *Die Stropers* subverts these ideals. Janno is a burly and sporty sixteen-year-old farm boy who works tirelessly towards his parents’ ideals. Like his younger sisters, Janno is adopted, which not only brings into play questions of identity, but also his mother’s inability to bear children and fulfil her symbolic duty as *volksmoeder*. When a thirteen-year-old streetwise orphan, Pieter, is introduced into the family as their new brother, every notion of Afrikaner identity and masculinity is challenged.

Both boys are queer. Janno harbours a secret attraction to the school head boy. Pieter is a recovering drug addict and prostitutes himself with older men.¹⁷ The boys represent different aspects of post-apartheid Afrikaner identity (Figure 17). Janno strives to uphold the ideals and conforms to the Afrikaner traditions of the past while trying to suppress his sexuality. Since homosexuality is considered sinful and abnormal,

¹⁶ 72% of agricultural land is in the hands of white farmers despite white people making up just 8% of the South African population (DRDLR 2018).

¹⁷ Not an eyebrow was raised in the Afrikaner community about the minors engaging in sexual activity, unlike the furore unleashed with *Inxeba*.

it is 'suppressed as an alternative expression of masculinity through isolation and a conspiracy of silence' (Du Pisani 2001, p.169). Pieter represents the future, proof that Afrikaner identity can be constructed in relation to Africa and Africanness. In addition to his nonbinary sexuality, he socialises with the black farmworkers, sings an African lullaby to his sisters and blends in comfortably with immigrants from Africa and China at the nearby Chinatown. Pieter sets himself further apart from the family and the community when he refuses to go to church and declares that they have been 'brainwashed' by religion, and when he tells Janno's friends, 'you think this is the real world *boertjies* [little farmers], [...] this is fucking nowhere.'

Pieter and Janno in *Die Stropers*.

Kallos (2019) finds variations on homosexuality attractive 'as a (back)way into exploring masculinity in a world currently obsessed with re-evaluating patriarchy.' Even though traditionally the father's role, it is the mother, Marie, 'that upholds the systemic patriarchy' (E. Kallos 2019, personal communication, 30 May). Marie imposes the stereotypes of hegemonic masculinity on her children and her values are deeply entrenched in Calvinism. This is already evident in the film's opening sequence that shows Janno herding cattle. The first words spoken are a nondiegetic voiceover: a prayer by Marie, which becomes her mantra. 'Dear Father God, make the boy strong, make his blood strong, make his seed strong.' Religion permeates the narrative, dialogue and mise-en-scène (Figures 18–20).

Figure 18

An embroidery of Da Vinci's 'The Last Supper' in *Die Stropers*.

Figure 19

A cross on a wall in *Die Stropers*.

Figure 20

Wanna stick your small Boer cocks
in my hole, faggots?

Religious graffiti on a town wall in *Die Stropers*.

Its queer content made production of the film difficult. On the one hand Kallos received no funding from the Afrikaans sector in the film industry 'because the film was too dark,' and on the other hand he couldn't secure any funding from the UK or USA 'because the content did not vilify the Afrikaners enough' (E. Kallos 2019, personal communication, 30 May). Recently a long-running colloquy of conspiracy against white farmers and the myth of a 'white genocide' gained ground with US President Donald Trump, who stepped into the fray by tweeting about 'the large-scale killing of white farmers' and the expropriation of land (McKenzie and Swails 2018; Rizzo 2018; Head 2019). Trump's interference had a profound effect on the fortunes of the film which, at the time of writing, has failed to secure distribution in the UK and USA. Kallos also claims that because Trump tweeted support for white South African farmers and because the film acknowledges farm murders, people wrongly assume he supports white nationalism and Trump (E. Kallos 2019, personal communication, 31 May).

CONCLUSION

Inasmuch that Lindsey Green-Simms (2018) observes that *Skoonheid* does not celebrate queerness, this study shows that other post-apartheid queer cinemas are not celebrations of queerness either. Queerness in South Africa—as elsewhere—is heterogeneous. This first generation of South African queer films spotlights themes of sexuality in a predominantly queerphobic society by exposing sexual violence, sexual abuses and suppressed sexualities. This study also illustrates that by redefining what it is to be masculine, these films actively participate in contemporary debates about masculinity and contribute to breaking down barriers of gender conformity.

By revealing previously hidden sexual practices, post-apartheid queer cinemas are creating space for the expression of new sexualities and alternate masculinities, despite evidence that the general South African public is (still) reticent to engage with queer films. None of these films have been box office or financial successes, certainly not proportional to their production costs or to comparable international productions. The dismal commercial performance of practically all post-apartheid South African queer films is summarised in Appendix 2. Data of a cohort of international queer films, as screened in South Africa, are provided in comparison. Despite several of these South African films being strong productions with strong individual impact, their potentially influential roles in the conversations of a society in the grips of tumultuous social transformation were drastically curtailed by their poor reception and uptake by that very society.

Astrid Treffry-Goatley (2010) notes that half of South African films fail to recoup ten percent of their production costs at the local box office. The 2018 box office report of the National Film Foundation in South Africa shows a decline in market share of South African-produced films from eleven percent in 2012 to only three percent in 2018. The cause may be that 'audiences continue to show support for international movies rather than local ones' (Tunzi 2018, p.3). This observation may be indicative of the supposition that a liberal constitution does not guarantee social recognition of nonnormative

sexualities, certainly a subject requiring further investigation in which film studies may be a surprising contributor.

Despite the recent upsurge of queer representations in South African cinema, audiences outside the films' countries of origin and the rest of Africa are much more engaged with the subject than local audiences. Imruh Bakari (2000) believes that the perception and purpose of African films are 'disproportionately determined by the response and reception of African films outside of the continent' (pp.4–5). Some scholars consider the fact that many of these productions are financially assisted by Europe and North America, and therefore tailored to suit the expectations of the market in the Global North, as a possible reason for their poor reception and performance in their respective countries of origin (Treffry-Goatley 2010; Osinubi 2019a). African filmmakers have a predicament when wishing to pursue their aspirations 'within the highly charged arena of Africa's political economy' (Bakari 2000, p.4), even more so for producers of queer content disavowed in and by their own countries.

African opponents of queer rights will probably never be convinced that films financed by the West or by South Africa (these for many Africans being the same thing) can speak with authentic African voices (Epprecht 2008). Such co-productions continue to fuel the fire of those politicians and theologians who cite them as examples of corrupting Western influences which threaten 'authentic Africanness' (Epprecht 2008, p.157). Christopher Meir (2018) reports that despite the fact that transnational film financing enables 'ideologically progressive filmmaking' (p.230)—as exemplified by *Skoonheid*—there is a perception in the local film industry that outsider interests and agendas 'such as themes of reconciliation, human rights and social problems' are imposed on local filmmakers (Ebrahim and Ellapen 2018, p.173).¹⁸ Similarly, questions raised by Ellapen (2018) about international co-productions, their intended markets and their influence on representations of the black African masculine—perfectly illustrated by the *Inxeba*

¹⁸ *Skoonheid* is a South African/French/German co-production. *Inxeba* is a South African/German/Dutch/French co-production. *Die Stropers* is a South African/French/Greek/Polish co-production.

controversy—must be considered when investigating representations of African identities.

Manthia Diawara (2000) once claimed that European funding forces African cinema into a position that prevents it from becoming cinema but rather occupy television slots or screen in cinemas intended for anthropological documentaries. Ngūgī Wa Thiong’o (2000) chastised the younger generation of filmmakers for being too far removed from the political struggle and ‘seduced into thinking that the success of their ventures lies in their escape from the social and political [...] in the hope of attracting finance and support from the West’ (p.241). Although these claims are today considered somewhat outdated, there is truth in Diawara’s theory that international audiences ‘go to see African films as realities about Africa, instead of seeing them as films’ (p.82). African cinema has tried to move beyond documentary, didacticism and polemics, and produced queer films which function mainly to normalise same-sex relationships in the pursuit of entertainment and, arguably, profit (Epprecht 2011). The films *Karmen Gei* (Joseph Gaï Ramaka, 2001) and *Rafiki* (Wanuri Kahiu, 2018) are two examples.

During fieldwork on gay identities in rural South Africa, Graeme Reid (2013) uncovered ‘widespread discomfort’ with the gender and sexuality ideals enshrined in the South African constitution (p.223). Opposition in communities on a micro-level contributes to the broader political and evangelical discourse that ‘gays are un-Christian and un-African’ which indeed points to a complex path ahead for queer films and filmmakers (Reid 2013, p.222). However, Etienne Kallos seems positive about the future of queer cinema in South Africa, especially from his experience in approaching children and parents at traditionally conservative schools during casting *Die Stropers*. Nobody shied away from the gay content, ‘they were just excited that I was saying something new about Afrikaners’ (E. Kallos 2019, personal communication, 31 May).

The continuous engagement with the subject by local filmmakers and artists, despite many obstacles, is undoubtedly encouraging, not only for the film industry but also for the unfinished struggle for gender equality.

Appendix 1. Equality Clause in the Bill of Rights of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa (Republic of South Africa, President's Office 1996)

9. Equality

- 1. Everyone is equal before the law and has the right to equal protection and benefit of the law.**
- 2. Equality includes the full and equal enjoyment of all rights and freedoms. To promote the achievement of equality, legislative and other measures designed to protect or advance persons, or categories of persons, disadvantaged by unfair discrimination may be taken.**
- 3. The state may not unfairly discriminate directly or indirectly against anyone on one or more grounds, including race, gender, sex, pregnancy, marital status, ethnic or social origin, colour, sexual orientation, age, disability, religion, conscience, belief, culture, language and birth.**
- 4. No person may unfairly discriminate directly or indirectly against anyone on one or more grounds in terms of subsection (3). National legislation must be enacted to prevent or prohibit unfair discrimination.**
- 5. Discrimination on one or more of the grounds listed in subsection (3) is unfair unless it is established that the discrimination is fair.**

Appendix 2. South African Theatrical Attendance and Box Office for Selected Post-Apartheid Queer Films

Table of South African Theatrical Attendance and Box Office for Selected Post-Apartheid Queer Films

<i>South African Productions</i>				
TITLE	ATTENDANCE	BOX OFFICE (ZA Rand)	PRINTS	RELEASE DATE
Proteus (2003)	1,392	R32,252	festival only	13 March 2004
The World Unseen (2007)	2,410	R77,380	6	13 February 2009
Disgrace (2008)	17,889	R550,635	10	14 August 2009
Skoonheid (2011)	10,701	R370,164	10	05 August 2011
While You Weren't Looking	1,779	R70,036	4	25 October 2015
Johnny is nie dood nie (2016)	9,800	R556,050	25	05 May 2017
Inxeba (2017)	35,180	R1,958,812	19	02 February 2018
Die Stropers (2018)	2,019	R123,683	10	15 March 2019
Kanarie (2018)	21,971	R1,454,590	23	19 October 2018
<i>African Productions</i>				
TITLE	ATTENDANCE	BOX OFFICE (ZA Rand)	PRINTS	RELEASE DATE
Dakan (1997)	320	R3,926	festival only	not available
Woubi Chéri (1998)	80	R1,526	festival only	not available

Table of South African Theatrical Attendance and Box Office for Selected International Queer Films

<i>International Productions</i>				
TITLE	ATTENDANCE	BOX OFFICE (ZA Rand)	PRINTS	RELEASE DATE
Beautiful Thing (1996)	15,392	R196,815	not available	not available
Happy Together (1997)	2,249	R35,851	1	not available
All About My Mother (1999)	23,819	R446,153	3	not available
Boys Don't Cry (1999)	26,129	R480,843	4	not available
Brokeback Mountain (2005)	103,922	R2,681,048	18	10 March 2006
A Single Man (2009)	22,736	R709,952	not available	not available
Carol (2015)	16,504	R912,728	13	18 December 2015
Moonlight (2016)	16,280	R882,558	9	10 February 2017

Information courtesy of South African distributors Ster-Kinekor, Indigenous Film Distribution, Empire Entertainment and UIP.

Filmography

Dakan (Destiny) (dir. Mohamed Camara, 1997)
Die Stropers (The Harvesters) (dir. Etienne Kallos, 2018)
Difficult Love (dir. Zanele Muholi and Peter Goldsmid, 2010)
Enraged By A Picture (dir. Zanele Muholi, 2005) (short film)
Films4Peace: Zanele Muholi (dir. Zanele Muholi, 2013) (short film)
Fools (dir. Ramadan Suleman, 1997)
Inxeba (The Wound) (dir. John Trengove, 2017)
Johannesburg (dir. Ian Forster, 2018)
Johnny is nie dood nie (Johnny is not dead) (dir. Christiaan Olwagen, 2016)
Kanarie (Canary) (dir. Christiaan Olwagen, 2018)
Karmen Geï (dir. Joseph Gaï Ramaka, 2001)
Lost in the World (dir. Xolelwa 'Ollie' Nhlabatsi, 2015) (short film)
Mapantsula (dir. Oliver Schmitz, 1988)
Quest for Love (dir. Helena Nogueira, 1988)
Rafiki (dir. Wanuri Kahiu, 2018)
Sarie Marais (dir. Joseph Albrecht, 1931)
Shield and Spear (dir. Petter Ringbom, 2014)
Skoonheid (Beauty) (dir. Oliver Hermanus, 2011)
Sleeper's Wake (dir. Barry Berk, 2012)
South Africa's 'Corrective Rape' Culture (dir. Iris Lebrun, 2015) (short film)
The Man Who Drove With Mandela (dir. Greta Schiller, 1998)
The Shadowed Mind (dir. Cedric Sundstrom, 1988)
The Soldier (dir. Matthew Krouse, 1988)
The Wooden Camera (dir. Ntshaveni wa Luruli, 2003)
Touki Bouki (dir. Djibril Diop Mambéty, 1973)
Tsotsi (dir. Gavin Hood, 2005)
While You Weren't Looking (dir. Catherine Stewart, 2015)
Woubi Chéri (dir. Laurent Bocahut and Philip Brooks, 1998)
Zonk! (dir. Hyman Kirstein, 1950)

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